

Evaluating Software Platforms for Digital Twins Creation: Features, Capabilities, and Trade-offs

-APPENDIX-

Daniel Flores-Martin^{ORCID}, *COMPUTAEX, Extremadura Supercomputing Center, Spain*, Aranzazu Rodriguez-Cabanillas^{ORCID}, *University of Extremadura, Spain* and Javier Berrocal^{ORCID}, *University of Extremadura, Spain*

This Appendix presents a detailed comparison of three representative platforms for Digital Twin implementation: Amazon AWS IoT TwinMaker, Microsoft Azure Digital Twins, and Eclipse Ditto. Each case explores the main architectural components, integration mechanisms, key functionalities, and practical deployment approaches of the respective platform. The objective is to provide a comprehensive overview that highlights the technological characteristics, benefits, and specific use cases of each solution, facilitating informed decision-making for developers and researchers working with Digital Twin systems.

APPENDIX A AWS IoT TWIN MAKER

AWS IoT TwinMaker is a comprehensive service within the AWS IoT ecosystem that specializes in generating Digital Twins by integrating operations from physical and digital systems. Its primary functionality lies in simplifying the creation of digital representations by measuring and analyzing sensor data and enterprise applications in the physical environment, enabling effective monitoring of infrastructures such as factories [1].

This service is broadly available across various global regions, including the Eastern and Western United States, Asia-Pacific, and Europe [2]. It supports the integration of predefined components accessible from the console, as well as the flexibility to design custom components to connect to various data sources, such as geospatial coordinates and telemetry streams [3].

AWS IoT TwinMaker offers a plugin for Amazon Managed Grafana and integrates seamlessly with other AWS services like AWS IoT SiteWise, forming a Digital Twin development architecture as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. AWS TwinMaker architecture.

A. Features and Functionalities

One of the key features of AWS IoT TwinMaker is entity modeling, which allows for the representation of devices, equipment, spaces, and processes. These models are connected to data sources such as sensors, cameras, and business applications through built-in connectors for AWS IoT SiteWise or through custom connectors for data stored elsewhere.

Another prominent feature is visualization, as AWS IoT TwinMaker uses 3D scenes to represent the physical environment and overlay relevant data, facilitating user understanding. Additionally, it supports the import of existing 3D models.

In terms of entity components, the platform enables the creation of composite component types, offering flexibility and efficiency when building complex components. This is complemented by a unified data access API that provides streamlined access to underlying data sources without the need to query each source individually.

Integration with Grafana allows the development of dashboard-based applications for end users.

B. Integration with AWS Services

This section outlines the operation of services and tools required to create a Digital Twin using AWS IoT TwinMaker.

1) AWS IoT Core

AWS IoT Core is a service that enables the connection of a large number of IoT devices with cloud-hosted applications and other devices. It facilitates efficient and secure device-to-cloud interaction, as well as the processing and analysis of large volumes of data generated by these devices [4].

This service includes a rules engine that allows automated actions to be defined based on data received from devices. These actions can trigger various processes such as invoking Lambda functions, storing data in Amazon S3, sending notifications through Amazon SNS, or inserting records into Amazon DynamoDB, among others.

Additionally, AWS IoT Core supports the creation of objects known as "Things," which represent connected devices and allow communication via the MQTT protocol. These objects help manage and monitor IoT devices while enabling real-time data exchange and command execution [5].

2) AWS Lambda

AWS Lambda is a serverless computing service that allows code to be executed without the need to manage infrastructure. It handles all aspects required to run and scale code with high availability, allowing it to be triggered automatically by events from other AWS services or called directly from web or mobile applications. Lambda functions can respond to events such as data changes, HTTP requests, and data analytics workflows, among others.

AWS Lambda integrates with other services, enabling Lambda functions to process data from AWS IoT Core and forward the results and metrics directly to services like AWS SiteWise for storage, visualization, and further analysis.[6].

3) AWS IoT SiteWise

AWS IoT SiteWise is a service that simplifies the organization, collection, and analysis of industrial data from connected devices. It enables organizations to monitor and manage equipment and industrial processes more efficiently and accurately, improving productivity and reducing operational costs [7].

The integration of AWS IoT SiteWise with Amazon Lookout for Equipment—a machine learning service—allows businesses to detect anomalies in equipment performance. This integration enables users to leverage machine learning models from Amazon Lookout for Equipment to proactively identify potential issues in industrial equipment monitored by AWS IoT SiteWise [8].

Furthermore, this service can be automatically integrated with AWS IoT TwinMaker, allowing for comprehensive management of both data and the creation of Digital Twins. These Digital Twins, based on data stored in SiteWise, are updated automatically and continuously. This integration enhances predictive maintenance and improves operational efficiency in industrial environments [9].

4) Amazon Lookout for Equipment

Amazon Lookout for Equipment is a machine learning service designed for anomaly detection and fault diagnosis in industrial equipment. It uses machine learning models to analyze data from sensors and real-time processes, identifying anomalous patterns that may indicate potential equipment failures.

The service obtains the required data from Amazon S3, AWS's cloud storage solution [10].

5) Amazon S3

Amazon Simple Storage Service (Amazon S3) is an object storage service that offers a secure and scalable way to store large volumes of data. It is designed to store and retrieve data with high durability and availability through a simple web interface [11].

6) AWS IAM

The IAM service provides secure control over access to resources on the platform. It enables centralized management of permissions that define which users can access specific AWS resources [12]. This functionality is essential for ensuring security and compliance within a cloud infrastructure environment, allowing for precise and granular access management.

7) AWS IAM Identity Center

AWS IAM Identity Center is a comprehensive solution offered by AWS for managing and controlling user access to platform resources. This service centralizes access and security policies, enabling administrators to efficiently define and manage access privileges across AWS. The primary function of IAM Identity Center is to provide a robust layer of security and compliance by managing identities and access within a scalable and dynamic cloud environment [13].

8) Amazon Managed Grafana

Amazon Managed Grafana is a data visualization and analytics solution that enables the creation of custom dashboards for monitoring and analyzing data from various sources within AWS and external systems.

A distinctive feature of Amazon Managed Grafana compared to self-hosted Grafana is its deep integration with other AWS services. This includes the ability to access and visualize data directly from native services such as Amazon CloudWatch, Amazon Elasticsearch, and Amazon S3. This integration not only simplifies the configuration and management of data connections, but also leverages AWS's scalable and secure infrastructure to ensure the availability and performance of dashboards and visualizations [14].

The service facilitates the creation of interactive charts and control panels that are fundamental for monitoring applications, infrastructure, and cloud services. Additionally, it offers advanced customization and collaboration features, allowing users to tailor data visualizations to their specific needs and efficiently share information within teams and organizations.

C. Implementation

Implementing a Digital Twin in AWS involves using several key tools and services from the platform to create a virtual representation of a physical asset or complex system. This Digital Twin not only replicates the structure and behavior of the physical object but also enables its monitoring, functional simulation, and predictive analysis. The development process is outlined below.

First, it is necessary to register with AWS, which involves creating an account and gaining access to the following services required for Digital Twin development:

- AWS IoT Core
- AWS Lambda
- AWS IoT SiteWise
- AWS IAM
- AWS IAM Identity Center
- AWS IoT TwinMaker
- Amazon Managed Grafana
- Amazon Lookout for Equipment
- Amazon S3

1) Data Capture with AWS IoT Core

The first step in creating a Digital Twin is the creation of an IoT object in AWS IoT Core, which registers and represents a physical device in the cloud. The purpose of creating this object is to allow a physical device—such as one running the Windows operating system—to operate with AWS IoT.

When generating this object, the operating system (Windows) and a compatible SDK (Node.js) must be specified. Once the configuration is complete, a software development kit (SDK) is generated for the device. This SDK includes a sample program that publishes MQTT messages. It is essential for connecting to AWS IoT services, as it provides the necessary access keys and includes documentation on how to configure permissions, run the sample script, and subscribe to an MQTT client test for sending data.

To carry out the data transmission process, a subscription was created for a test client using the topic “sdk/test/js”. This allows monitoring of MQTT messages sent to the AWS account under that specific topic, as shown in Listing 1.

```
awsIotClient.publish("sdk/test/js", AWSIotQos.QOS0, roadJson.toString());
```

Listing 1. Example of sending data to the 'sdk/test/js' topic subscription.

The data sent to the client subscription is formatted in JSON, as shown in Listing 2. Among the required fields is the asset name, which must be unique for each asset to allow correct identification when updating data.

```
1 JSONObject roadJson = new JSONObject();
2
3 String assetName = "road-" + currentRoad.getRoadId();
4 roadJson.put("assetName", assetName);
5
6 roadJson.put("roadId", currentRoad.getRoadId());
7 roadJson.put("name", currentRoad.getName());
8 roadJson.put("numberOfVehicles", currentRoad.getNumberOfVehicles());
9 roadJson.put("averageSpeed", currentRoad.getAverageSpeed());
10 roadJson.put("entryDate", currentRoad.getEntryDate());
```

Listing 2. Example of constructing a JSON object.

2) Creating Asset Models in AWS IoT SiteWise

Before transmitting data to AWS IoT SiteWise, it is necessary to define the models corresponding to each of the JSON objects to be transmitted. Based on these models, assets with identical structure will be generated, with only the property identifiers differing.

It is also important to define the hierarchy of the models. For example, an asset of type Road will be associated with assets of types Tunnel, District, and Entry.

3) Defining Interaction Rules with Services

Once the data is captured by the object defined in AWS IoT Core, it is necessary to define rules in AWS IoT. These rules enable devices to interact with AWS services. In this implementation, rules were created to invoke AWS Lambda functions, which then transmit the data to AWS SiteWise.

The first step is to define an SQL statement, such as the one shown in Listing 3, that specifies the source and name of the data to be used in the rule. In this case, the source table corresponds to the topic subscription name, which is “sdk/test/js”.

```
1 SELECT assetName, roadId, name, numberOfVehicles, averageSpeed, entryDate FROM 'sdk/test/js'
```

Listing 3. Example of an SQL query for an IoT Core rule.

The next step involves selecting the type of action the rule will perform. Here, a Lambda function is invoked to transmit the message data. To implement this function, a client must be defined to interact with AWS IoT SiteWise using Boto3¹.

Once the rule is configured, an AWS IoT trigger is automatically added to the Lambda function, indicating that it is associated with an AWS IoT rule, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Trigger defined in the Lambda function.

After creating the client, it is crucial to capture the data sent by the device that matches the properties specified in the SQL statement. This will allow storing or creating the corresponding assets. To correctly update the data, it is necessary to have the identifier of one of the active models defined in AWS IoT SiteWise and each of its properties, as shown in Listing 4. This must be done for all the model's properties that need to be updated.

```
1 property_id_num_vehicles = 'id'
2
3 entries = []
4 entries.append({
5     'entryId': str(uuid.uuid4()),
6     'assetId': asset_id,
7     'propertyId': property_id_number_vehicles,
8     'propertyValues': [
9         {
10            'timestamp': timestamp,
11            'value': {
12                'integerValue': num_vehicles
13            }
14        }
15    ]
16 })
```

Listing 4. Updating an asset in AWS IoT SiteWise.

Once all fields have been updated, the data must be sent to AWS IoT SiteWise so it can be properly processed and stored, as shown in Listing 5. If there is an existing asset with the same name as the one stored in the variable *assetName*, its values will be updated, and the update timestamp will be changed to the one indicated in the system. Otherwise, a new asset will be created with the corresponding values.

```
1 response = sitewise_client.batch_put_asset_property_value(entries=entries)
```

Listing 5. Sending data to IoT SiteWise.

4) Creation of alerts in AWS IoT SiteWise

When the data is automatically updated and received by AWS IoT SiteWise, alerts can be generated based on this data. For the generation of these alerts, two key aspects must be considered:

- **Definition of required attributes for the alert.** The attributes required to generate the alert must be previously defined in the model, as it is not possible to compare with external values or manually include data.
- **Creation of a user in IAM Identity Center.** A user must be created in IAM Identity Center, with an assigned email address to receive notifications when any of the established conditions are met.

Next, when defining the alert, an IAM user must be included to receive the notifications via the specified email address. It must also be specified when an alarm notification should be sent and the severity of the alert, as shown in Figure 3.

¹Boto3: Python SDK developed by AWS to interact with AWS services.

Property

averageSpeed

Property

LESS

Value

Choose an attribute containing the value to be compared. This attribute applies to all alarm properties associated with this alarm by default.

AverageSpeedMin

Severity

Alarm severity. Use a number your device can understand to reflect the severity of this alarm.

8

Severity must be an integer

Fig. 3. Definition of the alert threshold for the averageSpeed attribute.

Each time the alert is triggered, the user will receive an email message indicating the reason the alert was activated and its severity.

5) Integration of AWS IoT SiteWise and AWS IoT TwinMaker

Once all assets have been generated in SiteWise, the AWS IoT SiteWise service can be automatically integrated with AWS IoT TwinMaker, resulting in the creation of the workspace “IoTSiteWiseDefaultWorkspace (Linked Service: SiteWise)”. An IAM execution role must be specified, which must contain access permissions for the different services. Then, the generated workspace contains all the entities stored in AWS IoT SiteWise and by properly configuring the execution role, the data will remain updated.

6) Definition of a scene in AWS IoT TwinMaker

The configuration of a scene in AWS IoT TwinMaker begins with uploading the existing 3D model. Since AWS IoT TwinMaker supports 3D models in GLB or GLTF format, just like Azure 3D Scenes, the same 3D model will be used.

Once the model has been imported into the scene, the content of the annotations must be defined. The updated content is only visible in Amazon Managed Grafana. AWS IoT TwinMaker indicates and locates the data to be visualized. In this case, information related to the district, sensor, and road is displayed, as shown in Figure 4. These data, along with the graphs generated in Grafana, enable the control and management of the data received by the Digital Twin.

Fig. 4. Visualisation of an AWS IoT TwinMaker scene.

7) Integration of AWS TwinMaker with Amazon Managed Grafana

The integration of AWS IoT TwinMaker with Amazon Managed Grafana enables the visualisation of 3D models, providing a visual representation of the managed physical asset. To work with Amazon Managed Grafana, a workspace must be created in which one of the verification options is selected to access the service. In this case, the IAM Identity Center option is used, with a user who has been granted administrator permissions in Amazon Managed Grafana. Subsequently, it is necessary to configure the data access points, of which two have been used in this case.

- **AWS IoT TwinMaker.** From which the configured 3D model is obtained.
- **AWS IoT SiteWise.** Allows retrieval of historical data uploaded via the MQTT test client.

The next step is the configuration of the panels in Amazon Managed Grafana, as shown in Figure 5. To visualise the information about the M-30, several panels have been created that include the 3D model configured in AWS IoT TwinMaker, information related to the number of vehicles on the road, sensor intensity in district 2, and the current average speed to travel the M-30 from the A-2 entry point.

Fig. 5. Panels defined in Amazon Managed Grafana.

8) Integration with AWS Lookout for Equipment to make predictions

To complete the Digital Twin, it is necessary to make predictions about the number of vehicles on the M-30. To this end, AWS has natively integrated AWS IoT SiteWise with Amazon Lookout for Equipment [14]. The predictions made in Amazon Lookout are based on data collected over 14 days and stored in AWS IoT SiteWise’s historical data. These predictions indicate whether the next predicted value is valid or not, as shown in Figure 6, allowing identification of whether the obtained values are normal or otherwise, flagging them.

Prediction definition ID	Prediction definitions	Training status	Inference status	Prediction results
0086bd62-a657-417d-8200-1a970c62bcfe	completePrediction	✔ Data training completed	✔ Active	✔ Normal

Fig. 6. Prediction result from Amazon Lookout for Equipment.

Additionally, a file is stored in the default-created bucket indicating the prediction results, as shown in Listing 6.

```

1 {
2   "timestamp": "2024-06-14T17:30:00.000000",
3   "prediction": 0,
4   "prediction_reason": "NO_ANOMALY_DETECTED",
5   "diagnostics":
6   [
7     {
8       "name": "cfd8ec7d-cd49-4b52-9392-c05608bd7b14\\cfd8ec7d-cd49-4b52-9392-c05608bd7b14",
9       "value": 0.48461
10    },
11    {
12      "name": "7e466d9d-73ba-4cc8-aa97-310f9b36b82c\\7e466d9d-73ba-4cc8-aa97-310f9b36b82c",
13      "value": 0.51539
14    }
15  ]
16 }

```

Listing 6. Prediction result for Carretera (Road)

The prediction result indicates that no anomaly was detected in the Road data, with a prediction of 0 and the reason “NO_ANOMALY_DETECTED”. This means that, according to the system’s analysis, no unusual patterns or conditions indicating problems or risks in the Road-0 asset were observed at that time. In addition, information is provided on the value associated with the prediction, which is 0.48461. This value is consistent with the historical analysis, where a similar value of 0.51539 was found, confirming the normal state of the Road-0 asset at that moment.

APPENDIX B AZURE DIGITAL TWINS

Azure Digital Twins is an Internet of Things (IoT) platform provided by Microsoft that enables the development of digital representations of real-world places, things, people, and business processes using a model description language (DTDL)² [15]. This cloud-based platform is highly scalable and offers a wide variety of services across multiple geographical regions. It relies on a secure and scalable architecture that allows for the creation and storage of Digital Twins.

Azure Digital Twins is available in several geographical regions, including Southeast Asia, East Australia, Central Qatar, South Korea Central, Central US, South Central US, East and West US, Northern and Western Europe, East Japan, and South UK. These deployment zones enable users to manage Digital Twins and connect IoT devices and enterprise systems across the globe [16].

The architecture depicted in Figure 7 is based on a collection of servers and network hardware responsible for executing a set of distributed applications. These applications manage the configuration and operation of virtualized hardware and software on the servers, providing a versatile environment for different types of deployment scenarios.

Fig. 7. Architecture of Azure Digital Twins.

In a complete solution using Azure Digital Twins, essential architectural elements are identified, as represented in the diagram in Figure 7, which outlines a broader Azure IoT solution. The architectural elements are as follows [17]:

- **IoT Hub instance.** This component plays a key role by providing essential functionalities for device management and data flow in the IoT context.
- **Azure Digital Twins instance.** A service that enables the creation of Digital Twins through its twin graph and supports 3D model visualization.
- **Alert rule.** Used to trigger alerts when values fall outside the defined acceptable range.
- **Azure Function instance.** Enables code execution in response to events without requiring infrastructure management. It facilitates the development of scalable applications by automatically running functions.

A. Features and Functionalities

Azure Digital Twins offers features that enhance its versatility and adaptability across diverse business contexts. Its capability to define a custom vocabulary and use an open modeling language enables the creation of tailored models for various connected environments [18].

One notable feature is its live execution environment, which allows for the creation of Digital Twins through a real-time representation of a dynamic graph, facilitating real-time decision-making.

Azure Digital Twins' ability to integrate input from IoT and enterprise systems is essential for connectivity and interoperability. It enables the connection of IoT devices via Azure IoT Hub and REST API, providing a robust interface for data and event integration.

Moreover, the system supports output twin change events routed through services such as Azure Data Explorer and Event Hubs, enhancing responsiveness and adaptability to environmental changes [17].

In terms of functionality, Azure Digital Twins not only tracks the past but also helps forecast the future of connected environments, eliminating data silos and offering real-time insights.

The platform enables the development of connected solutions for enterprise IoT, monitoring, managing, and updating IoT devices with both security and scalability by integrating with Azure IoT Hub. This comprehensive approach redefines the management of physical entities and business processes, driving digital transformation and enterprise-grade IoT optimization [17].

²DTDL. Open-source language developed by Microsoft to describe and define data models within the Azure Digital Twins platform.

B. Digital Twins Definition Language

A key feature of Azure Digital Twins is its ability to define custom vocabulary and automatically generate Digital Twin graphs. These models are expressed using the Digital Twins Definition Language (DTDL), which is based on JSON-LD. Although DTDL is primarily used with Azure Digital Twins, it is not exclusive to this service and can also be used to represent data for other IoT services [19].

Understanding the core components of the DTDL language and defining the fields of a model interface are critical steps in the effective design and implementation of models within Azure Digital Twins.

These components provide a solid structure for representing and managing Digital Twins, thereby facilitating interoperability and data integration in IoT environments.

Properly specifying the interface fields and carefully selecting DTDL elements establishes a foundation for creating robust and scalable models in Azure Digital Twins. This enables the efficient and precise management of digital entities and their relationships in a variety of industrial and business scenarios. [20].

C. Integration with Azure Services

This section explains the operation of the services and tools required to generate a Digital Twin using Azure Digital Twins.

1) Azure IoT Hub

A key feature of the IoT device management service within Azure Digital Twins is its integration with the Azure IoT Hub. This managed, cloud-hosted service acts as a messaging hub, facilitating communication between all connected devices and an IoT application. Essentially, it manages connectivity and communication between the cloud and IoT devices [17].

Combining Azure IoT Hub and Azure Digital Twins ensures efficient IoT device management and enables the development of more advanced IoT solutions. From monitoring and control to integration with additional Azure services, this collaboration offers a comprehensive approach to overcoming challenges and capitalising on opportunities in the IoT space.

2) Azure Functions

Azure Functions is an event-driven serverless compute platform that automatically scales workloads by increasing or decreasing the number of resources based on demand. It supports various programming languages, such as C#, PowerShell, JavaScript, Python, and more [21].

This service can be integrated with Azure IoT Hub through an IoT Hub trigger. This allows the creation of Azure Functions that are triggered every time a new message is received by the IoT Hub. This trigger is based on an Azure Event Grid binding, which enables scalable and secure event responses [22].

3) Azure Event Grid

Azure Event Grid is a managed event routing service that enables the development of applications with event-based architectures. It simplifies the creation of event-driven applications and serverless workflows [23].

Events can be generated by Azure services, custom applications, or third-party applications. It is a highly scalable service that ensures real-time event delivery. It is ideal for scenarios such as automating processes when files are uploaded to Azure Blob Storage or reacting in real time to changes in Azure resources [22].

4) Azure Digital Twins Explorer

This tool allows developers to visualize and interact with the data from an Azure Digital Twins instance, including the twin graph and models. It is essential for exploring the twin graph in detail, as well as modifying Digital Twins and their relationships within the graph context [24].

This tool is used for validation, investigation, and retrieving specific information about Azure Digital Twins. It also enhances the understanding of digital representations in real-world contexts. Its investigative capabilities allow querying specific properties of Digital Twins, models, or relationships, making it a comprehensive resource for managing and understanding Digital Twins.

5) Azure 3D Scenes Studio

This tool is designed to simplify the deployment of interactive 3D environments linked to Digital Twins, allowing users to create, edit, and visualize 3D scenes. It enables organizations to enhance pre-existing 3D models with data-driven visualizations powered by Azure Digital Twins. Importantly, Azure 3D Scenes Studio does not require users to have prior experience with 3D technologies.

The functionality of this tool is based on the concept of scenes, which refers to a specific view of a unique business environment represented in three-dimensional data [25]. The supported scenes must be in GLB or GLTF format, with a file size not exceeding 100MB.

To use 3D Scenes Studio, users must have an Azure Digital Twins instance and an Azure Storage account. In addition, it is necessary to configure a private container in the storage account, where the access type must be set to either "Storage Blob Data Contributor" or "Storage Blob Data Owner", and CORS (Cross-Origin Resource Sharing) must be enabled for the corresponding storage account [25]. These configurations ensure efficient deployment and effective integration with Azure Digital Twins technologies.

6) Azure Machine Learning

Azure Machine Learning is a cloud-based service that enables the efficient building, training, and deployment of machine learning models. It provides a scalable and integrated environment for managing models, conducting experiments, and deploying machine learning solutions.

This tool supports the optimization and automation of these processes, including data preparation, algorithm selection, and hyperparameter tuning. It also offers a wide array of prebuilt tools and algorithms for deep learning and machine learning that users can leverage to build sophisticated models.

7) Azure Monitor

Azure Monitor is a monitoring and analytics service that allows users to collect, analyze, and visualize data from cloud applications and services, as well as from on-premises devices and systems [26].

The alerting capabilities of Azure Monitor allow users to define rules based on logs or resource activity in the cloud. When these rules are met, the service can automatically send notifications, such as emails or SMS messages, to alert users about potential issues or anomalies in their applications or infrastructure. This alerting functionality helps operations teams detect and respond quickly to important events, minimizing the impact on service availability and performance [27].

D. Implementation

Implementing a Digital Twin in Azure Digital Twins involves creating and managing accurate digital representations of real-world objects, processes, and systems. This process consists of several key stages that ensure consistency, functionality, and scalability of the Digital Twin.

The first step is to register in Azure, which involves creating an account and configuring the following services:

- Azure IoT Hub.
- Azure Functions.
- Azure Event Grid.
- Azure Digital Twins.
- Azure Monitor.
- Azure Machine Learning.

1) Creation of the Digital Twin Graph

The initial step in creating a Digital Twin in Azure, after configuring the required services, is to generate its graph of Digital Twin instances, which is based on the principle that all model instances must be related to another instance. The outcome of this process is a set of nodes or Digital Twins connected through relationships in a graph.

SDK Coding

With the necessary Azure services configured, the next step is to create a project using .NET Core 3.1, a framework that provides the tools required to develop robust and efficient applications. The Azure CLI must be installed³, allowing users to log in to Azure via the command line. The first step is authenticating with the Azure Digital Twins service. For this purpose, a client class has been created to access the SDK functions. The host name of the Azure Digital Twins instance is required for authentication, as shown in Listing 7.

```

1 string adtInstanceUrl = "https://<your-Azure-Digital-Twins-instance-URL>";
2 string adtInstanceUrl = "";
3 DigitalTwinsClient client = null;
4 try{
5     var credential = new DefaultAzureCredential(
6         new DefaultAzureCredentialOptions { ExcludeSharedTokenCacheCredential = true }
7     );
8     client = new DigitalTwinsClient(new Uri(adtInstanceUrl), credential);
9     Console.WriteLine("Service client created - ready to go");
10 }

```

Listing 7. Installation of the Azure CLI.

Model Upload

The types of entities that Azure Digital Twins can represent must be defined in models. To create a Digital Twin, at least one model must be defined in DTDL and stored in “.json” files, such as the one shown in Listing 8.

```

1 {
2     "@id": "dtmi:Entry;1",
3     "@type": "Interface",
4     "displayName": "Entry",
5     "@context": "dtmi:dtidl:context;2",
6     "contents": [
7         {
8             "@type": "Property",
9             "name": "entryName",

```

³Azure CLI. A set of command-line tools for creating and managing Azure resources.

```

10     "displayName": "Name of the entry",
11     "schema": "string",
12     "description": "Name of the segment entry."
13   },
14   {
15     "name": "entryDate",
16     "displayName": "Entry date",
17     "@type": "Property",
18     "schema": "dateTime",
19     "description": "Date on which the data was stored."
20   },
21   {
22     "@type": "Relationship",
23     "name": "contains",
24     "displayName": "Contains",
25     "target": "dtmi:Segment;1"
26   }
27 ]
28 }

```

Listing 8. Example of a DTDL file in JSON format.

For this Digital Twin implementation, six models were defined to represent the structure of the M-30 (Listing 7): Road.json, District.json, Entry.json, VehicleSensor.json, Section.json, Tunnel.json. The next step is to enable the generated code to interact with the Azure service. This involves adapting the code to load DTDL files and store them in an Azure Digital Twins service instance. Once the models are defined, they can be viewed in Digital Twins Explorer, where the accepted and properly formatted models are listed, as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. List of models uploaded to Azure Digital Twins.

Creation of Digital Twins

Next, Digital Twins are created based on the previously uploaded model definitions. This process involves instantiating models, in order to for which a specific method has been developed for each of the uploaded models. Each method is tailored to the structure of the corresponding model, identified using the “ModelId” variable. The model with the identifier “dtmi:Road;1” is used, as shown in Listing 9.

```

1  var twinData = new BasicDigitalTwin{
2      Id = $"{prefix}{road.RoadId}",
3      Metadata = { ModelId = "dtmi:Road;1" }
4  };
5
6  twinData.Contents.Add("roadId", road.RoadId);
7  twinData.Contents.Add("name", road.Name);
8  twinData.Contents.Add("vehicleCount", road.NumberOfVehicles);
9  twinData.Contents.Add("averageSpeed", road.AverageSpeed);
10 twinData.Contents.Add("entryDate", road.EntryDate);
11 entryDateString = road.EntryDate.ToString("yyyy-MM-ddTHH:mm:ss.fffz");
12
13 try {

```

```

14     await client.CreateOrReplaceDigitalTwinAsync<BasicDigitalTwin>(
15         twinData.Id, twinData
16     );
17
18     string primaryKey = await AzureIoTHub.GetDeviceAsync(twinData.Id);
19     var messageString = JsonSerializer.Serialize(road);
20     await AzureIoTHub.SendCloudMessageAsync(
21         primaryKey,
22         twinData.Id,
23         messageString
24     );
25 }
26
27 catch (RequestFailedException e) {
28     Console.WriteLine($"Create twin error: {e.Status}: {e.Message}");
29 }

```

Listing 9. Example of creating an instance of type Carretera

Creating Relationships

Once the model instances are defined, relationships must be established between them to connect them into a Digital Twin graph, as illustrated in Listing 10. This step is essential for representing the complete M-30 environment.

```

1 public static async Task CreateRelationshipAsync(
2     DigitalTwinsClient client, string srcId, string targetId, string name
3 ){
4     var relationship = new BasicRelationship { TargetId = targetId, Name = name };
5
6     try {
7         string relationshipId = $"{srcId}-{name}->{targetId}";
8         await client.CreateOrReplaceRelationshipAsync(srcId, relationshipId, relationship);
9     } catch (RequestFailedException e) {
10        Console.WriteLine($"Error creating relationship: {e.Status}: {e.Message}");
11    }
12 }

```

Listing 10. Example of creating a relationship between Carretera and Tunnel.

The method “CrearRelacionAsync” handles the creation of relationships between all Digital Twin instances. It requires three parameters:

- **string srcId.** Source of the relationship, e.g. “Road-0”.
- **string targetId.** Target of the relationship, e.g., “Tunnel-0”.
- **string name.** Descriptive name of the relationship between the instances, such as “containsTunnel”, representing that “Road-0” contains “Tunnel-0”.

Once all the data has been uploaded, Azure Digital Twins Explorer displays a graph of twins like the one shown in Figure 9, where the model instances and their relationships can be visualized.

Fig. 9. Graph in Azure Digital Twins Explorer.

2) 3D Model

Azure Digital Twins Explorer offers the capability to export and visualize 3D models to graphically represent the data using Azure 3D Scenes. A 3D model in GLB or GLTF format must be imported. In this case, Blender 4.0 was used to create a small road segment representing a portion of the M-30.

Once the model is imported, each element must be linked to a corresponding Digital Twin instance so that it can reflect real-time values. Additionally, it allows defining visualization rules to indicate the status of each sensor, using colors or icons, as shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Visualization rule definition in Azure 3D Scenes.

Once each sensor is linked to its corresponding model instance and visualization rules have been set, the 3D model can be run to display the behavior of the sensors, as observed in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. Visualization of the 3D model in Azure 3D Scenes.

3) Updating the Digital Twin

After the creation of the twin graph, it is necessary to continuously update the data whenever new values are received, which in this case occurs every 5 minutes. This process follows the workflow shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 12. Data flow diagram from IoT Hub to Azure Digital Twins [28].

To carry out the data update process in Azure Digital Twins Explorer, Azure IoT Hub and Azure Functions must be configured. This setup allows data collected by IoT devices to be processed and sent to Azure Digital Twins in real time, facilitating data-driven decision-making.

Azure Function Configuration

Creating an Azure Function is essential to update the Digital Twin in Azure Digital Twins [28]. To achieve this, a new Azure Functions project is created with an Event Grid trigger. Visual Studio Code is used to load the information into the Azure platform.

To configure authentication and create a client for interacting with Azure Digital Twins, an object named “ManagedIdentityCredential” is used to authenticate the Azure Function via a managed identity. Then, a “DigitalTwinsClient” object is instantiated using the URL of the Azure Digital Twins instance, the credentials, and client options, including setting up the HTTP transport using a previously created “HttpClient” to ensure that all HTTP requests are made through it, as shown in Listing 11.

```

1 var cred = new ManagedIdentityCredential("https://<your-Azure-Digital-Twins-instance-URL>");
2 var client = new DigitalTwinsClient(new Uri(adInstanceUrl),
3   cred,
4   new DigitalTwinsClientOptions {
5     Transport = new HttpClientTransport(httpClient)
6   }
7 );

```

Listing 11. Configuration of an Azure Digital Twins client.

Finally, a function is defined for each model type to process messages received from IoT devices and update the corresponding Digital Twin in Azure Digital Twins. The function extracts several data fields from the device message—for instance, in “ProcessRoadDataAsync”, it extracts roadId, name, vehicle count, average speed, and entry timestamp. A “JsonPatchDocument” is then created to define the update operations to be applied to the Digital Twin, as shown in Listing 12.

```

1 private static async Task ProcessRoadDataAsync(
2   JObject deviceMessage,
3   DigitalTwinsClient client,
4   ILogger log
5 ){
6   DateTime entryDateDateTime;
7   string deviceId = (string)
8   deviceMessage["systemProperties"]["iothub-connection-device-id"];
9
10  var roadId = deviceMessage["body"]["RoadId"];
11  var name = (string)deviceMessage["body"]["Name"];
12  var vehicleCount = deviceMessage["body"]["VehicleCount"];
13  var averageSpeed = deviceMessage["body"]["AverageSpeed"];
14  var entryDate = deviceMessage["body"]["EntryDate"];
15
16  log.LogInformation(
17    $"Device: {deviceId}, RoadId: {roadId}, Name: {name}, VehicleCount: {vehicleCount}, AverageSpeed: {averageSpeed},
18    EntryDate: {entryDate}"
19  );
20
21  var updateTwinData = new JsonPatchDocument();
22  updateTwinData.AppendReplace("/roadId", roadId.Value<int>());
23  updateTwinData.AppendReplace("/name", name);
24  updateTwinData.AppendReplace("/vehicleCount", vehicleCount.Value<float>());
25  updateTwinData.AppendReplace("/averageSpeed", averageSpeed.Value<float>());
26
27  if (DateTime.TryParse(entryDate.ToString(), out entryDateDateTime)) {
28    string entryDateISO = entryDateDateTime.ToUniversalTime().ToString("o");
29    updateTwinData.AppendReplace("/entryDate", entryDateISO);

```

```

29     } else {
30         log.LogError($"Could not parse 'EntryDate' to DateTime: {entryDate}");
31     }
32
33     await client.UpdateDigitalTwinAsync(deviceId, updateTwinData);
34 }

```

Listing 12. Example of Road data processing.

Azure IoT Hub Configuration

Once the Azure Function is properly configured, a device must be connected to registered in Azure IoT Hub with the corresponding Azure Digital Twin. When the device emits telemetry data, this information is processed by the “ProcessHubToDTEvents” function, which triggers an update in the Digital Twin. This ensures that the Digital Twin remains synchronized with the real-world device.

It is essential to have an Azure IoT Hub instance properly configured, as its *HostName* is required for the program to send the corresponding data to the Azure instance. The data is sent to Azure IoT Hub by retrieving the “primaryKey” and “deviceName” of the instance to be updated. These variables enable device identification, as shown in Listing 13.

```

1 public static async Task SendCloudMessageAsync(
2     string primaryKey, string deviceName,
3     string messageString
4 ) {
5     string deviceConnectionString =
6         $"HostName={hubName}.azure-devices.net;DeviceId={deviceName};SharedAccessKey={primaryKey}";
7
8     var deviceClient = DeviceClient.CreateFromConnectionString(deviceConnectionString);
9
10    var message = new Microsoft.Azure.Devices.Client.Message(
11        Encoding.UTF8.GetBytes(messageString)
12    ) {
13        ContentType = "application/json",
14        ContentEncoding = "utf-8"
15    };
16
17    await deviceClient.SendEventAsync(message);
18    Console.WriteLine($"{DateTime.Now} > Sending message: {messageString}");
19 }

```

Listing 13. Sending data to Azure IoT Hub.

4) Alert Generation

To complete the real-time monitoring aspect of the Digital Twin, alerts must be generated based on the updated data in the twin graph. This process combines Azure Digital Twins, Azure Functions, Event Grid, and Azure Monitor. Azure Monitor is responsible for detecting when a value falls outside of the predefined parameters and allows the severity of each notification to be specified.

Diagnostic Configuration

The first step is to ensure that Azure Digital Twins is configured to send metrics and logs to Azure Monitor. This is done by accessing the “Diagnostic Settings” window and adding a previously created workspace. In this case, the default workspace “DefaultWorkspace-079” is used. When configuring diagnostics, it is necessary to specify the log categories to be collected. Two options were selected in this setup:

- **DigitalTwinsOperation.** Includes general operation logs performed in Azure Digital Twins. Useful for tracking service interactions.
- **QueryOperation.** Records details of query operations executed within the Digital Twins service.

Azure Monitor Configuration

In Azure Monitor, under the Alerts section, it is necessary to configure an alert. In this case, it is done under the Azure Student subscription used to create the account.

Alerts are configured using Kusto Query Language⁴ to filter and analyze the data sent to the Digital Twin. These data are stored in the “AppTraces” table, from which the query must extract the relevant information for the alert.

In this example, the most recent value entered into the historical dataset is retrieved, and only those records where the road name matches “M-30”. Once verified, an alert is triggered if the number of vehicles exceeds 9,000 vehicles/hour.

```

1 AppTraces
2 | where tostring (Properties) contains "NumberOfVehicles"
3 | extend PropertiesJson = parse_json(Properties)
4 | extend OriginalFormat = tostring(PropertiesJson['prop__{OriginalFormat}'])
5 | extend Parts = split(OriginalFormat, ", ")
6 | extend
7     ID = tostring(split(Parts[1], ": ")[1]),
8     Name = tostring(split(Parts[2], ": ")[1]),

```

⁴Kusto. A language used for analyzing large volumes of telemetry and log data, allowing filtering, analysis, and visualization of information.

```

9 |     NumberOfVehicles = toint(split(Parts[3], ":")[1]),
10 |     AverageSpeed = todouble(split(Parts[4], ":")[1]),
11 |     EntryDate = todatetime(split(Parts[5], ":")[1])
12 | | where Name == "M30"
13 | | order by TimeGenerated desc
14 | | take 1
15 | | extend Alerta = iif(NumberOfVehicles > 9000, "Warning of more than 9.000 vehicles on the M30.", "Normal")
16 | | project TimeGenerated, ID, Name, NumberOfVehicles, AverageSpeed, EntryDate, Alert

```

Listing 14. Example of a Kusto query.

Once the alert is configured and enabled to send notifications to a specific email address, it becomes visible in the Azure Monitor window. This view displays details about the alert value at the time it was triggered—9,770 in this case—with a deviation of 770 vehicles, as shown in Figure 13.

Fig. 13. Details of an alert triggered by vehicle count on the M-30 (I/II).

A notification is also sent to the specified email address, explaining the reason for the alert. The message includes information such as the alert name, a brief description, alert level, and the timestamp of the event.

5) Generating Predictions

The prediction process in the Azure environment is carried out using the Azure Machine Learning platform. This tool allows for the efficient creation, training, and deployment of machine learning models by leveraging Azure's scalable and robust infrastructure.

Creating a Function

To facilitate the transfer of data from Azure Digital Twins to Azure Blob Storage, an Azure Function named "DigitalTwinToTableStorage" has been implemented. This function enables the storage of Digital Twin data.

Once deployed in Azure, it is necessary to create an Event Grid subscription to ensure continuous data updates.

To efficiently handle events in Azure, the Event Grid must be configured. This includes creating a Topic in Event Grid and configuring Azure Digital Twins to send events to that Topic. Next, the endpoint in Azure Digital Twins must be set up, linking the event route to the Event Grid Topic. This ensures that data from Azure Digital Twins is automatically sent to the created Function, where it is processed and stored in the "blobM-30" Blob Storage.

To verify and configure Azure Event Grid, a subscriber is added to the created Topic. This subscriber receives events and routes the data to the "DigitalTwinToTableStorage" Function, ensuring that the data updated in Digital Twins is correctly processed and stored.

APPENDIX C ECLIPSE DITTO

Eclipse Ditto is an IoT technology developed under the Eclipse Foundation that implements Digital Twins to represent millions of instances in the digital domain. This implementation simplifies the development of IoT solutions for software developers [29]. As an open-source platform, it can be installed and executed on both local and cloud-based servers, offering flexibility in controlling its geographic availability based on specific needs and requirements. It also enables software modification without requiring a usage license.

It is not a complete IoT platform—meaning it lacks a full suite of tools or services for designing, developing, and managing IoT solutions. It does not provide software that runs on IoT gateways and does not define or implement IoT protocols to facilitate device communication [29]. Instead, it relies on a microservices architecture, with each service dedicated to specific tasks such as access policy management, connectivity, or *Things* management.

In its most practical deployment, Eclipse Ditto services are implemented using Docker containers. These containers can be managed manually or integrated into higher-level orchestrators like Kubernetes. The only external dependency required by Eclipse Ditto is the use of the NoSQL MongoDB database, which is responsible for storing connections, logs, events, and other relevant records. Additionally, NginX⁵ can be optionally used to support the web interface and basic user authentication tasks [30].

The architecture of Eclipse Ditto, shown in Figure 14, is based on an infrastructure composed of servers and network devices that coordinate application execution. These components play a crucial role in monitoring the configuration and operation of both hardware and software, providing a flexible environment adaptable to various settings and requirements specific to Eclipse Ditto.

Fig. 14. Eclipse Ditto Architecture.

A detailed breakdown of the Ditto architecture reveals a set of microservices that perform specific roles [31], [32]:

- **Policies.** This microservice is responsible for enforcing the defined authorization policies.
- **Things.** Manages the storage and administration of the system's IoT devices.
- **Gateway.** Provides a system access interface via HTTP and WebSocket protocols.
- **Connectivity.** Enables message transfer using the Ditto protocol, forwarding messages to external brokers and receiving messages from them.

A. Features and Functionalities

Eclipse Ditto stands out as an advanced tool for managing Digital Twins and IoT devices, supported by several key features. As an open-source platform, it encourages community collaboration and continuous development. Its scalable architecture allows it to handle large volumes of data and devices, ensuring efficient performance even in highly complex environments [30].

A major strength lies in its seamless integration with IoT devices, using JSON to interact via commands and events, ensuring flexibility in managing Digital Twins. Its ability to detect real-time changes and generate events and notifications is complemented by Eclipse Hono, delivering a comprehensive solution for device and Digital Twin management in IoT ecosystems.

Additionally, Eclipse Ditto is distinguished by its robust access control and API authorization mechanisms, ensuring data security and confidentiality. It abstracts the Digital Twin through both synchronous and asynchronous APIs, enabling efficient management of the reported, desired, and current state of devices.

Acting as IoT middleware, Ditto facilitates device integration using protocols such as MQTT and Eclipse Hono, and it can also interface with existing backend systems. In summary, Eclipse Ditto is a comprehensive and versatile solution that addresses critical aspects of Digital Twin and IoT device management in advanced technology environments.

⁵**NginX.** An open-source web server used to enhance the performance and security of online services.

B. Thing Definition Language in Eclipse Ditto

A Thing in Eclipse Ditto is modeled using a data structure composed of the following elements:

- **PolicyId.** A unique identifier of the policy containing the required authorization information. It must follow the entity ID format with namespace notation.
- **Attributes.** A JSON object describing the Thing's static properties. Attributes represent characteristics that do not change frequently.
- **Features.** An object that holds the dynamic features of the Thing. Each feature is identified by a unique featureId. It is recommended to use a restricted set of characters for featureId naming.

This structure enables modeling of different types of entities within a policy management system, clearly distinguishing between static data (attributes) and dynamic data (features), while maintaining a history of creation and modifications for each Thing.

C. Integration with Eclipse Ditto Services

This section details the operation of the services and tools required to build a Digital Twin using Eclipse Ditto.

1) Kubernetes

Kubernetes is an open-source platform that automates the operation of Linux containers, facilitating the deployment and scalability of applications across container clusters. It works closely with Docker to manage containers, automating deployments, load balancing, self-healing, and scaling applications in public, private, or hybrid cloud environments.

Eclipse Hono, a project aimed at connecting IoT devices with backend services, is effectively deployed using Kubernetes. This enables the use of automation capabilities to handle high-frequency communication and large volumes of data in distributed environments. To ensure proper deployment of Eclipse Hono, the Kubernetes cluster must be version 1.11 or higher.

The configuration and management of a Kubernetes cluster requires specific tools such as:

- **Kubectl.** A command-line tool used to communicate with a Kubernetes cluster [33].
- **Helm.** A package manager for Kubernetes that allows defining, installing, and updating Kubernetes applications [34].

2) Docker Desktop

Docker is a software platform designed to simplify the process of building, testing, and deploying applications through containerization. These containers are standardized units that encapsulate everything needed to run an application, including libraries, system tools, code, and runtime. [35].

In the context of Digital Twin development using Eclipse Ditto, the use of Docker images for platforms such as Eclipse Ditto, Eclipse Hono, and Eclipse Mosquitto is essential. These tools are critical for the effective implementation and management of Digital Twins, enabling the simulation and control of physical objects in a virtual environment through efficient interconnection and communication between devices and services.

3) Eclipse Hono

The service responsible for managing IoT devices in Eclipse Ditto is Eclipse Hono, an open-source platform designed to facilitate communication among IoT devices. Its primary function is to provide remote service interfaces that enable a wide range of IoT devices to connect to the backend and interact uniformly, regardless of the communication protocol they use [36].

Additionally, a public-access sandbox environment is available, aimed at providing a platform to experiment with devices and learn how to connect them to Eclipse Hono without the need to configure a local instance [37]. The Eclipse Hono sandbox instance includes the following components and service ports, as shown in Table I.

Component	Service port(s)
Device register	28443 (HTTP 1.1/TLS)
Protocol adaptator AMQP	5671 (AMQP 1.0/TLS)
Protocol adaptator CoAP	5684 (CoAP/DTLS)
Protocol adaptator HTTP	8443 (HTTP 1.1/TLS)
Protocol adaptator MQTT	8883 (MQTT 3.1.1/TLS)
Message infrastructure (AMQP)	15671 (AMQP 1.0/TLS)
Message infrastructure (Kafka)	9094 (Kafka/TLS)

TABLE I
COMPONENTS AND SERVICE PORT FOR ECLIPSE HONO [37].

4) Eclipse Mosquitto

Eclipse Mosquitto is an MQTT message broker, using a lightweight messaging protocol specifically designed for constrained devices and networks with low bandwidth, high latency, or unreliable conditions. This protocol is widely used in IoT environments, as it enables efficient communication and data exchange between connected devices and systems.

It serves as an open-source message intermediary between Eclipse Hono and Eclipse Ditto through the MQTT protocol implementation. This protocol provides an efficient and lightweight mechanism for message transmission based on the publish/subscribe model, making it well-suited for IoT messaging [38].

5) PostgreSQL

PostgreSQL is a widely used relational database management system known for its reliability and robustness. It offers a wide range of advanced features, such as ACID-compliant transactions, foreign keys, and triggers. Additionally, it is highly extensible and compatible with various operating systems, facilitating its integration into diverse applications and use cases [39].

This tool is used in combination with MQTT as an intermediary between Eclipse Ditto and Grafana. This setup is necessary because Grafana is not designed to directly receive messages via HTTP.

6) Grafana

Grafana is an open-source analytics and monitoring platform that allows the visualization of data from various sources through customizable dashboards. It is widely used in the context of IoT due to its ability to integrate with different data sources, including PostgreSQL, InfluxDB, and Prometheus.

In the Eclipse Ditto environment, Grafana is employed to visualize data from Digital Twins. Alerts can be configured based on specific conditions, such as exceeding a vehicle count threshold. These alerts can then be visualized in the dashboard interface.

D. Implementation

The first step involves cloning the Eclipse Ditto repository from GitHub and building the corresponding image using Docker. Afterwards, connectivity is checked using the Eclipse Hono sandbox, which allows testing without the need to install Hono locally, as it provides a public experimentation environment for working with connected devices. This procedure ensures the correct implementation of the Digital Twin using Eclipse Ditto, meeting the requirements and making use of the platform's functionalities.

1) Creating the access policy

Once the Eclipse Ditto image is configured and started in Docker, it is necessary to access the user interface to configure the access policy for the resources that will be generated in the system. These policies regulate access to the Thing within the Eclipse Ditto environment. For the development of this case study, a policy has been defined with the identifier "org.eclipse.ditto:twins-policy", which must be unique to guarantee the correct identification and management of the policies within the system. In the specified policy, the variable `nginx:ditto` is defined, which represents the name of the user with access to this policy. Also, reading and writing permissions are granted for each of the specified elements, as shown in the Listing 15. This configuration ensures that the user has the necessary permissions to interact with the Thing, policies, and messages, allowing both reading and writing to each of these resources.

```

1 {
2   "policyId": "org.eclipse.ditto:twins-policy",
3   "imports": {},
4   "entries": {
5     "DEFAULT": {
6       "subjects": {
7         "nginx:ditto": {
8           "type": "generated"
9         }
10      },
11     "resources": {
12       "thing/": {
13         "grant": [
14           "READ",
15           "WRITE"
16         ],
17         "revoke": []
18       },
19       "policy/": {
20         "grant": [
21           "READ",
22           "WRITE"
23         ],
24         "revoke": []
25       },
26       "message/": {
27         "grant": [
28           "READ",
29           "WRITE"
30         ],
31         "revoke": []
32       }
33     },
34     "importable": "implicit"
35   }
36 }
37

```

Listing 15. Example of an Eclipse Ditto policy.

2) Communication protocol

One of the key aspects of managing the Thing in Eclipse Ditto is setting up a connection using the MQTT protocol. This protocol enables communication between physical devices and their respective Digital Twins via an MQTT broker, the definition of which requires setting the URI, message addresses, access permissions, and failover capability. In this configuration, the broker URI used is “tcp://test.mosquitto.org:1883”, which indicates the use of the TCP protocol and standard port 1883 for MQTT connections. Another important aspect is the definition of source and destination addresses, such as “addresses: [eclipse-ditto-sandbox/#]”, which allows capturing all messages within a test environment. Furthermore, it is essential to define an incoming mapping via JavaScript, which is responsible for dynamically processing and adapting the content of the received payload. This is done by the “mapToDittoProtocolMsg” function, which interprets the data and adjusts the characteristics and attributes of the Thing according to the structure expected by Eclipse Ditto.

The construction of a protocol message in Eclipse Ditto is done using the “Ditto.buildDittoProtocolMsg” function, which is designed to handle the structure of all sent Things. This process is detailed in the Listing 16.

```

1 return Ditto.buildDittoProtocolMsg(
2     thingId[0],
3     thingId[1],
4     'things',
5     'twin',
6     'commands',
7     'modify',
8     '/',
9     headers,
10    payload
11 );

```

Listing 16. Construction of a Ditto protocol message.

3) Creation and Sending of Thing

Once the connection with Eclipse Ditto has been established, the process of data transmission is enabled through the implementation of a Java programme that acts as an intermediary between physical devices and the platform. This programme allows for the periodic and automated transmission of relevant information to the Digital Twins, establishing bidirectional communication between the devices and Eclipse Ditto. In this way, remote monitoring, dynamic configuration, and efficient resource management are made possible. To achieve this, it is necessary to generate a JSON object that describes the attributes and characteristics of the Thing, including a unique identifier and the name of the previously defined access policy. The “sendMQTTData” class is responsible for managing the transmission of this information using the MQTT protocol. This class establishes a connection with the MQTT broker and sends messages in JSON format, as shown in Listing 17.

```

1 private static final String MQTT_BROKER = "tcp://test.mosquitto.org:1883";
2
3 public static boolean sendMQTTData(String jsonData, String topic) {
4     MqttClient client = null;
5     try {
6         String clientId = MqttClient.generateClientId();
7         client = new MqttClient(MQTT_BROKER, clientId, new MemoryPersistence());
8         MqttConnectOptions connOpts = new MqttConnectOptions();
9         connOpts.setCleanSession(true);
10
11         if (!client.isConnected())
12             client.connect(connOpts);
13
14         MqttMessage message = new MqttMessage(jsonData.getBytes());
15         message.setQos(1);
16         client.publish(topic, message);
17         return true;
18     } catch (MqttException e) {
19         System.err.println("Error connecting to or sending the message via MQTT: " + e.getMessage());
20         e.printStackTrace();
21         return false;
22     } finally {
23         if (client != null) {
24             try {
25                 if (client.isConnected())
26                     client.disconnect();
27             } catch (MqttException ex) {
28                 System.err.println("Error disconnecting MQTT client: " + ex.getMessage());
29                 ex.printStackTrace();
30             }
31         }
32     }
33 }

```

Listing 17. Data transmission via the MQTT protocol.

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